

ЎЗБЕКИСТОН RESPUBLIKASI SOғLIҚNI SAQLASH VAZIRLIGI
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TOШKENT TIBBIЁT AKADEMIIASI URГANЧ FILIIALI

«TIBBIЁTDA INNOVATSİYANING ЎRNI»
мавзусидаги Халқаро илмий-амалий анжуман тўплами

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН
МИНИСТЕРСТВО ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ, НАУКИ
И ИННОВАЦИЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН
ТАШКЕНТСКАЯ МЕДИЦИНСКАЯ АКАДЕМИЯ
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Ушбу илмий ишлар тўпламида тиббиёт олий ўқув юртлирида фаолият олиб бораётган профессор-ўқитувчилар бажараётган илмий-тадқиқот ишлари натижалари ўрин олган. Тезисларнинг мазмуни ва улардаги хатоликлар учун масъулият муаллифлар зиммасидадир.

В сборник научных трудов вошли результаты научно-исследовательских работ, проведенных профессорско-преподавательским составом медицинских ВУЗов. Тезисы не рецензируются. За содержание и достоверность указанной информации ответственность несут авторы.

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КИРИШ СЎЗИ

Хурматли халқаро илмий-амалий анжуман иштирокчилари!

Биз тиббиёт ва соғлиқни сақлаш соҳасидаги катта ўзгаришлар остонасида турибмиз. Айниқса, тиббиётда инновацияларнинг ўрнига кўпчилик қизиқиш билдирмоқда: беморлар, шифокорлар, тадқиқотчилар. Бу борада юртимизда турли кўламдаги ишлар амалга оширилмоқда. Олимларимиз ва етук мутахассисларнинг тиббиёт соҳасидаги инновациялар бўйича изланишлари билан, шунингдек бу борада олиб борилаётган илмий-тадқиқот ишлари билан танишишда ва ўзаро фикр алмашишда бундай илмий-амалий анжуманларнинг фойдали жиҳатлари кўп, деб ўйлайман.

Тошкент тиббиёт академияси Урганч филиалида 2024 йил 26-27 апрел кунлари ўтказиладиган “Тиббиётда инновациянинг ўрни” мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий анжуманининг ўтказилиши хорижий олимлар ва республикадаги етук мутахассислар билан тиббиётда инновацияларнинг ўрни юзасидан ўзаро фикр алмашиш ҳамда илмий-тадқиқот ишларини амалиётга тадбиқ қилиш имкониятини беради. Анжуманда ўқиладиган ҳар бир маърузада тақдим этиладиган янги маълумотлар илмий-тадқиқотчилар ва амалий шифокорлар фаолиятида муҳим аҳамият касб қилишига ишонаман.

Хурматли илмий-амалий анжуман қатнашчилари. Барчангизни халқаро илмий-амалий анжуманнинг бошланиши билан табриклайман ва ушбу анжуманнинг юқори даражада ўтишига тилак билдираман!

*ТТА Урганч филиали директори
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LABORATORY FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF PNEUMONIA ASSOCIATED WITH COVID-19 IN YOUNG CHILDREN

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The relevance of the problem: Pneumonia associated with coronavirus infection (COVID-19 pneumonia) is a special type of lung lesion that more accurately reflects the term "pneumonitis". This implies the involvement of interstitial lung tissue, alveolar walls and vessels in the pathological process. That is, inflammation develops in all structures of the lungs involved in gas exchange, which prevents normal oxygen saturation of the blood.

The purpose of the study: to study clinical and laboratory features of the course of pneumonia associated with COVID-19.

Material and methods: A study was conducted with the participation of 55 children (30 boys, 25 girls) hospitalized in COVID Cent from May 2020 to June 2021 with a diagnosis of COVID-19, moderate/severe course, pneumonia of viral/viral-bacterial etiology. The diagnosis was verified according to modern clinical and laboratory criteria for etiological diagnosis, including by detecting COVID-19 RNA in the smear material from the mouth and nasopharynx by polymerase chain reaction (PCR), as well as taking into account modern clinical and radiological criteria for viral lung damage using specialized methods of radiation diagnostics.

Research results: The analysis of the gender-age structure of the study group of patients revealed no significant differences in the incidence of COVID-19-associated pneumonia depending on gender. The age of the youngest patient was 2 years, the oldest — 15 years. Among the examined patients, the predominance of children over the age of 14 years was noted.

All patients were hospitalized in COVID Cent for emergency indications, of which 22 (40%) were delivered by transport of the emergency medicine center from district hospitals of the region, 17 (30.9%) were admitted by the direction of the district pediatrician, 14 (25.5%) children were delivered from home by ambulance teams, 2 more (3.6%) were hospitalized by self-referral.

Conclusion. Thus, among hospitalized patients with community-acquired pneumonia associated with COVID-19, there was a predominance of children over the age of 12 years. At the same time, 30.9% of patients had concomitant diseases, among which the most common were obesity, pathology of the cardiovascular system and the central nervous system. In addition, 63.6% of patients were diagnosed with concomitant respiratory infection, most often mycoplasma, pneumococcal and mixed mycoplasma-pneumococcal etiology.

TUBERCULOSIS AND ITS COURSE IN PATIENTS WITH HEPATITIS B

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The relevance of the problem: Tuberculosis is an infectious disease that most often affects the lungs and is caused by a certain type of bacteria. It spreads through the air when infected people cough, sneeze or expectorate. Tuberculosis is a social disease. Koch's wand does not distinguish between social status and infects the poor and the rich with equal effectiveness.

The purpose of our study: was to study the state of the hepatobiliary system of patients with drug resistant pulmonary tuberculosis.

Materials and methods of research: In the Khorezm regional tuberculosis dispensary, 263 patients with pulmonary tuberculosis were subjected to a comprehensive examination. Among these patients, 163 patients were diagnosed with a drug-resistant form of pulmonary tuberculosis, and 100 patients had a drug-sensitive form of pulmonary tuberculosis. Patients with drug-resistant form of pulmonary tuberculosis were aged from 18 to 67 years. There were 107 men (65.6±3.7%), 56 women (34.4±3.7%). In 114 (69.9±3.5%) patients, fibrous-cavernous pulmonary tuberculosis was diagnosed, in 37 (22.7±3.2%) – infiltrative, in 12 (7.4±2.0%) disseminated pulmonary tuberculosis. In all patients, the resistance of mycobacterium tuberculosis to anti-tuberculosis

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